

**WOMEN, LANGUAGE OF REVOLT AND NATION
BUILDING IN EFFIONG JOHNSON'S *INSTALL THE
PRINCESS AND NOT WITHOUT BONES*.**

By

Miriam Stephen **INEGBE**

Faculty of Arts, Department of English

Akwa Ibom State University (Obio Akpa Campus)

inegbemiriam@gmail.com

+234 803 7928 319

Abstract:

This essay starts on the assumption that African women do not enjoy the full privilege of contributing let alone being heard of in African society, they hover only on the fringes. Ekwierhoma, in *ododo* (2001:81) explains that society is the guilty party here... that beclouds the women's miserable existence". As such they are under constant psychological closure of how they could break out from the claws of tradition that idolizes and favours only men. The constant victimization, humiliation and assault meted out on the African woman, put her through daily psychological interrogations and questionings which have afforded her the quest and determination to discover herself and then redeem her dignity. This essay examines the place of women and their place in nation building with reference to Effiong Johnson's *Install the Princess and Not Without Bones*. These plays project explicitly the issue of gender conflict, and a new society built by women through revolt.

Introduction:

African literature has advanced and developed tremendously in terms of themes. Literary works have embraced themes like protests for freedom from colonial masters, struggle for an egalitarian society, liberation from corrupt leadership, political and social decadence as well as male hegemony among others. Early African literary writings were largely dominated by male writers. The themes treated and the different characterizations favoured only men. Women were

characterized as affiliates to men as well as low lives. Frank (1987:55) affirms this when he stated that;

Until recently, most African novels have been written by men and... women characters are defined in this novels by their relations to men.... shadowing figures... girl friend or good time girls, workers such as secretaries or clerks, wives and other male appendages, and prostitutes...

The above peculiarities, which also hold true for the drama genre, gave rise and courage to determined African women to start writing in order to redeem the image of the African woman. Among the early women writers were Aminata Sow Fall, Calixthe Beyala, Ama Ata Aidoo, Buchi Emecheta, Mariama Ba, and so on. These women, in their writings, anchored their views on the several traditional oppressions meted on the African woman and they advocated for a change.

There is always a change in the values of people from one generation to the other. In essence, societal values are never the same. They are dynamic in nature. To achieve a change in any society, parties involved may have to experience a social upheaval as well as different physical influences. Usually this leads to conflict and revolt for a better restructuring of society. Conflict is an essential factor if change must take place. This is why Burton (1990,136) insisted that "conflict, like sex, is an essential creative element in human relationship. It is the means to change; the means by which our social values of welfare, security justice and opportunities for personal development can be achieved..."

Revolt is the product of conflict. Revolt can as well be viewed as a situation that has degenerated to the use of protest to effect the needed change. Revolt is to rise to opposition (Schwarz et al 1990. 12-57) to cause radical change and revolution against unacceptable conditions. Hagher (1997:14) mentions the issues that could lead to revolt and radical protests as social injustice, insecurity of life and property, territorial ambition, national pride, religious intolerance, ideological differences, etc... (these) are the oils igniting the flames of war...

Revolt is an age long tool used in kicking against exploitation, oppression and domination. Revolt, therefore, is borne out of depression and other oppressive developments within the minds of the oppressed. The developments motivate their actions and of course the determination as well as their consciousness.

Zimbardo (1992:519) admits this through Sigmund Freud's theory of personality which states that every human action has a cause and purpose that can be discovered through psychoanalysis of thought associations, dreams. The above citation holds that the action of the oppressed emerges from their psychological consciousness to fight against oppression, in which they have found themselves. To achieve their dreams through revolt and protest against the injustices meted on them, awareness must be created. This is done through verbal art, which is language.

Language is an indicator of a people's times, dreams and condition. By this language is a medium through which a people's beliefs and values are communicated and transmitted from one generation to the other. This position agrees with Moore's (1967) assertion that to "choose a language is to choose a world". And wa Thiong'o adds that "the choice of language... pre-determines the answer to the most important question... (1981:53) Thus language embodies the soul of revolt and consciousness. Language contributes immensely to the social and cultural development of any society and it is a prerequisite for nation building. Language is a veritable tool in the development and creation of national consciousness in any society. Black and Coward, in Dale (1980:101) consider language "as an instrument of expression, the perceived interest of a given social group, whether men or women As such language is a significant cultural aspect of any given society. It is one of the most basic media used for nation building. This essay considers the employment of language as one of the major tools for revolt, by women in restructuring and building a new egalitarian society in two plays of Effiong Johnson.

Analysis of Plays:

Install the Princess and Not Without Bones were both written by Effiong Johnson, one of Nigeria's foremost playwrights. In the

plays, he dramatizes and examines the affairs, events and manner of doing things by indigenes of particular societies as well as campaign for change in his society. The playwright refutes the age-long belief that women only promote peace as he makes his female characters to play roles of militants, roles meant for men. He adorns his female characters with masculine carriage as they dare to do what Ebele Eko in Emenyonu (1989:243) describes thus "the new generation African woman is fast acquiring new skills, venturing with fortitude into new areas, becoming more politically aware, uniting with others towards greater community involvement and commitment to consciousness"

The above qualities are all seen in Effiong Johnson's female characters in the above selected plays. These women are forceful, and extraordinarily intelligent, talented and courageous. The playwright uses his female characters to arouse people's awareness to the need for a change. In *Install the Princess*, women of the fictitious land of Ekondo are traditionally and culturally positioned as silent and passive in relation to men who wield traditional power and authority. This is seen in the speech of Ufokiban,

All through the years, the throne of Ekondo always had male successors to the throne. Now it hasn't... (Install the Princess, 2009: 62)

The above statement shows how women in Ekondo are usually excluded from the decision-making process. In response to the above speech, one of the elders in council, Ukpotio argues that there is a successor, Etiowo, and that he can be made good even though he is disabled. This generates a lot of controversy as he has to state categorically to Ufokiban that "... The throne of Ekondo is exclusively for Kings and not for queens" (2009:62) Here, a stout argument erupts as Ufokiban attempts to restore their cultural values and insisted that "... the throne cannot be mounted by a disabled (2009:63) she further advocates that, what Ekondo needed at the moment was a change and declares that:

There has to be a change... that change is the Princess ascending the throne of her fathers... (2009:64)

Ufokiban is seen here as an activist and as an advocate of change in her community, Ekondo Her suggestion is that the Princess be

installed instead of a disabled Prince, Etiowo, to desecrate the throne and their cultural values. Ufokiban has a thorough wrestle with the elders of Ekondo:

Nkakat: There has to be the right change. That change is finding a male-`successor to the throne of Ekondo, other than Elbowo (2009:64)

This wanton display of male chauvinism and interest in the throne of Ekondo by the elders even at the moment of disaster shows how gullible and wicked the decision makers of Ekondo are. Ufokiban refuses to accept the elders' alternative of wanting to force a successor other than one from the royal lineage as she declares:

*But it has to be from the lineage of Obong Nkanang.... Not doing
so
will be sacrilegious (2009:64)*

Here Ufokiban is not just seen advocating for the continuity of lineage of Obong Nkanang but also as a custodian of their cultural beliefs and taboos so as to promote peace and progress in Ekondo. One of the elders, Nkakat still maintains:

*We're talking of different changes, you're talking of a female
sacrilegious leader for Ekondo (P.65)*

Nkakat's argument, here, gives rise to gender conflict. The playwright skillfully used this scenario to create awareness to certain vital issues especially how traditional culture is a burden on women. Ufokiban, being a woman with a great innate wisdom and ability goes ahead to advice and encourage change through the right way:

*While you're talking of a strange and an abominable male outside
the ruling family of Ekondo... and the only person without
deformity (and) acceptable to the sanctity of Ekondo royal throne,
is Princess (P.65)*

She is seen here as being forceful, as keeping quiet will be allowing the new open door for the women to be heard in Ekondo for once be

unjustly taken away. In the above conversation, the playwright has also revealed that conflict is an important aspect of life.

The gender conflict anticipates protest as the oldest woman in Ekondo, Nne Mmatim summons an all-women meeting at the market square so that they can collectively fight for their rightful positions in Ekondo. This act of Nne Mmatim agrees with Sigmund Freud's assertion that every human action has a cause and purpose that can be discovered" (Zimbardo 1992:519). Nne Mmatim reacts aggressively to the refusal of the elders to install Princess as the only eligible candidate for the throne. She declares the popular will of the women of Ekondo;

Elders of our land,...Everyday, the forgetter may forget the forgotten. But a day comes when the forgotten is remembered. That day has come in Ekondo We already sent words around to every woman in Ekondo. They should be waiting for us at the market square. We have only one message, namely; (P.80)

Women: *Install the Princess! (P. 80)*

Women of Ekondo decide to take their destiny in their hands, as they rise up to fight for their place, power and authority. Nne Mmatim persists:

...we shall visit the shrines of the fathers and shout to them (P.80)

Women: *Install the Princess (P.80)*

Nne Mmatim: We shall carry leaves and send our message through them to all the groves. We shall carry the dust of the earth and send messages through them to the graves And our message remains... (P.81)

Women: *Install the Princess!*

Nne Mmatim: Finally, we expect... all the male-cults of the land to resurrect for the last time today. We shall see them, but they shall also see our nakedness... my women, lets go.

It is clearly seen through the speech of Nne Mmatim and the women, that they are fully prepared ready for a justifiable change in leadership in Ekondo irrespective of anything. To them, the only antidote to sooth their oppression was giving women a space so that they can also be politically active by installing the princess who will eventually become their queen and ruler. They are seriously and vehemently opposed to the tradition that reserves the throne of Ekondo to "men and men alone" to quote Ukpotio in the play. To the men of Ekondo, it is an act of abomination for women to even suggest the princess let alone threaten to go protesting in governance and practice.

Eventually, the only seer in Ekondo is consulted, and it is the will of the gods for times and values to change. The elders of Ekondo, therefore, lose the struggle to keep a man on the throne through the intervention of natural phenomenon that is Etiowo, being deaf and dumb- and also through the strong opposition of the women. Thus, the culture and traditions of Ekondo have to change for the society to witness peace, order and progress. Women triumph over their traditional culture as the princess, a woman' is installed as the queen of Ekondo so as to answer the clarion call to also serve her father's land as one of the rulers of Ekondo. In her words,

If you all accept me as the Queen of Ekondo, let me hear your voices... (p. 104)

At her clarion call, there is great jubilation and dance. Declaring and installing the princess as Queen of Ekondo symbolize a declaration for change and victory over traditional culture. This change also projects an era of gender equality on the one hand, and reformation on the other which are governed by the values of modernity. Change in cultural values from one state to another is clearly observed and seen in the princess's lines here: "As a ruler I am qualified and have the right to choose myself a husband" (p. 106)

The above quotation clearly portrays an egalitarian society where everyone has equal right to do things. Here, the playwright has carefully and creatively modified certain aspects of Ekondo tradition to suit the new times and for a better society. It is glaring that the new

society is a modern one and it is full of values of modernity. This explains the reason why the Queen could choose herself a spouse of her choice. This new society is, therefore, a product of change, transformation, replacement, civilization and switch to new ways of doing things. Thus, the playwright, in a clearly realistic manner, rubbishes Ekondo's long-standing traditions and then employs women as revolutionaries to create a new society where a woman can also be empowered politically to rule. The playwright has, through this play, recommended that women be given space to politically become active.

Not Without Bones, another play written by Effiong Johnson has a colonial This mirrors the economic and political problems of the Opobo people of South-South Nigeria. The playwright makes the female characters his major concern, and of course the heroines of the play. The women in this play are actually not without bones as they rise up and successfully fight against exploitation, oppression and taxation on women's meagre earnings leveled on the Opobo people by the colonial masters.

In Not Without Bones, the colonialists, through their worrisome development and taxation policy in Opobo, have caused all taxable male adults in Opobo, to flee the village, leaving only their women behind. This feeling of insecurity and oppression in their land makes the women of Opobo to act fast and reverse the slavery that is imminent in their homeland:

We have assembled women because our men have failed. The men tried to fight the whitemen but what have could our arrows, spears and knives cause whitemen with their guns, gunboat and other superior weapons? Our village warriors and proud chiefs have all been crushed in repeated defeats by these strangers Now the remaining men do not even sleep in their houses again because they are asked to pay taxes which they can't afford and evading the task masters, they must. So we are the only ones left. We must unite and send the whitemen out of our country. (women react) (p.9)

The women of Opobo, led by Ekaiban are left with no other alternative but to take their destiny into their hands by becoming warriors, if they really must send the whitemen out of Opobo. This action by women of Opobo agrees with the Marxian view of life that stresses that "force tends to disrupt and transform the status quo rather than equilibrating

one.... (Olaniyan & Quayson, 2007: 122). The women of Opobo in *Not Without Bones*, deviate from the established character of women who always accept anything forced on them for peace to reign to that of militants or revolutionaries in an attempt to reclaim dignity, justice and liberty for themselves, their children, and their husbands. With great determination, strength and unity, the women of Opobo demolish and set ablaze a lot of the structures, buildings and offices of the whitemen. One of the policemen guiding some of these structures has this to say:

Police: Sir, we were at the court building when the women came to the place. We tried to stop their penetration into the court. They were too many for us. Too mad for us to stop. They set the court house on fire and almost threw us into the flames (p.33)

The postal agency, sir... fire is gutting the place. We were there when these wild women arrived, armed with all kinds of weapons (p.34)

Flyers: The women have brought down the church building....

The whitemen face the greatest shock of their lives even as the violence and brutal destruction come from mere women who are known to be peacemakers. The militancy of these women in their attempt to procure change, peace and progress in Opobo could be likened to Sembéne Ousmane's women characters in *God's Bits of Wood* where Ramatoulaye, Penda, Maimouna and other women activists revolt against exploitation and oppression which eventually leads to the end of the colonial encounter. This action becomes a source of strength and inspiration to the women in their struggle to defend their children, husbands, cultural values and the African dignity. The women militants in Opobo thus contribute enormously towards the re-building of Opobo kingdom through their unnatural reactions; they thus qualify as those who make the Opobo people look forward to their future with courage and pride. It is also through their radical reactions that the whitemen are compelled to go into dialogue, which culminates in an agreement with the terms set by the people of Opobo:

D.O: Please, women. I am willing to understand and co-operate with you.... Tell me everything here. (p.45)

Ekalban ... that government will not tax women (p.45)

Women must not be charged any fees for the use of common market shed
(p.46)

*3rd woman: Why should we obtain licenses before we perform our
ceremonies in our land?... This nonsense has to stop! (p.46)*

*2nd woman: Our men must not be asked to pay tax to the whiteman
again. Why should we become slaves in our land?*

D.O: I want to assure you... that your conditions shall be met promptly...

Thus, the radical reactions of the women of Opobo mark the turning point and of course the end to exploitation, oppression and women taxation in Opobo. It is largely through their demonstrations that the people of Opobo can look back on their past with pride and to the future with hope. This revolt and protest soothe away the psychological, economic, social and political trauma of the women; although some of the heroines in *Not Without Bones*, bear the brunt of the violent revolt through loss of lives. The playwright has through this play suggested that women be given space to become a part of the decision making process so as to build a strong, peaceful and viable nation.

Language of Revolt:

Within the context of this essay, Language is seen as that which predetermines the action of the female characters (women) in the selected plays of Effiong Johnson, just as wa Thiong'o (1981) admonished "the choice of language... pre-determines the answer to the most important question..." Language, therefore is a vital tool of revolt in the plays selected for this analysis. Revolt is the major weapon of change in the two plays selected, and it is driven by the people's consciousness. This consciousness is alerted or ignited through the people's verbal signposts, in which Thiong'o (1981:59) expatiates:

*...over time, a particular system of verbal signposts comes to reflect
a given people's historical consciousness of their... struggles over
nature and over the social product language thus comes to
embody... consciousness.*

In the above assertion of Thiong's, the character of language as one embodying cultural continuity and consciousness rousing people from one state to another in order to effect change is observed and identified use therefore, becomes a semiotic process based on people's choices. Change and gender equality achieved and registered in the plays are products of language of revolt. Whorf (1940:211) describes language thus:

...the background linguistics system (...) of each language is not merely a reproducing instrument for voicing ideas but rather is itself the shaper of ideas, the program and guide for the individual's mental activity, for his analysis of impression for his synthesis of his mental stock in trade

The transformations, reformations and change reflected in the two plays selected are made possible through radical reactions and of course language of revolt which is the two women leaders in the plays selected use respectively as an instrument for voicing and creating awareness of the oppression meted on them. Language is the instrument the ignite their consciousness to their situation as well as a guide for their mental activities. Through language, these women register their physical anger, is viewed in *Not Without Bones*:

Ekalban: (...) stinking, impotent slaves! If you had any serise at all, you wouldn't opt to be a broom in the hand of a stranger. (p. 15)
...We shall go at once to the stupid chief's house... (p.21)

Mark people, is not a shameful thing that you should become a slave in your own house? You are a disgrace to all your forefathers and a big shame to all of us women... (p.27)

Following the verbal utterances above, one could clearly see a physical language of insults and the use of obscene language as a way or means of revolting against the injustice done on them by their very own black brothers who have thrown their cultural values to the wind and parading themselves as slaves to the strangers (the whitemen).

In *Install the Princess*, the playwright dramatizes revolt and protest through language of blackmail, as viewed here:

Ufokiban: *If you don't leave now, I shall ask my woman to strip*

themselves naked for you to see them very well. (p.79)

Ukarakpa: *Yesterday too all the women of Ekondo, gathered in the market square, not to sell, but to invoke curses on all those who would connive to cheat and deprive them to their rights. They were ready to go naked and bathe in the sun crying with one voice, Install the Princess! (p. 102).*

Apart from the use of language of blackmail that is, threatening to strip themselves naked before the entire community of Ekondo, they also make use of sacred language of invocations, Incantations as well as curses, as a verbal means of revolt to embrace change in Ekondo as reflected the Ukarakpa's statement above.

Women and Nation Building:

It is often said that women are the weaker sex. The truth of this statement is questioned in *Install the Princess and Not Without Bones*. These two plays are products of contemporary and modern day Nigeria. The women in the two plays represent the advocates of change, modern era and a new society.

In Install the Princess, Ufokiban, the women representative in the elders forum is seen trying to guide the cultural values of Ekondo, when she declares categorically that the successor to the throne has to be from the lineage of Ogong nkanag... not doing so will be sacrilegious" (p.64)

It is clearly seen in this line, that Ufokiban is more concerned with building a peaceful society in Ekondo as well preserving the cultural values of Ekondo, to avert any form of doom befalling their children as well as their society. This profuse confrontation of the elders and the reference to the lineage of the Late Obong Nkanang register the cultural orientation and nation building by the women. One can clearly see that Ufokiban, a woman is intelligently, courageously and immensely contributing to the wellbeing and growth of Ekondo by insisting that the right thing be done.

In Not Without Bones, women are also portrayed as people with "very strong bones" because they are strong willed. Even when the able men of Opobo kingdom fled the village of Opobo the women held sway. The courageous women of Opobo stood up to speak for themselves, their husbands, children and Opobo, their society thus:

...our village warriors and proud chiefs have all been crushed in repeated defeats by these strangers Now the remaining men do not even sleep in their houses again... so we are the only ones left, we must unite and send all whitemen out of our country (p.9)

The women of Opobo stand up to address their problems and that of the society, as the whites had created more problems already in their cultural construct. This singular act of determination to confront and send out the oppressive strangers shows that women care about the progress and peace of their society. The women fight against the exploitation and oppression meted on them, their husbands and society by the whites rulers on Opobo. Through these lines also, the women are also seen building the cultural values of Opobo:

Why should we obtain licences before we perform our ceremonies in our land? (p.46)

The women observe that Opobo culture and systems of operation have come under severe threat, no thanks to the whitemen's domination of Opobo. As such, they stand their grounds, and collectively fight to preserve and to keep their moral and cultural values as well as dignity. This strong willed and goal getters' women of Opobo triumph over the whitemen, and indeed successfully preserve their cultural values and their rights as citizens on Opobo. Through these women the land of Opobo witness peace, and change. It is pertinent to say that women in both societies - Ekondo and Opobo respectively defended and built their cultural values, promoted justice and morality as well as built a new egalitarian society through revolt so as to effect the necessary changes their societies needed.

Conclusion

Effiong Johnson has maintained a great interest in the development of an egalitarian society where there is no gender conflict. His two plays selected *Install the Princess and Not without Bones* are instruments of expressing his feelings about gender conflicts. His clever manipulations of character to express his desires and views concerning the African society is worthy of critical consent. That is what this work has attempted to do. Giving voice to African woman in a dramatization of this nature has redeemed the image and dignify of the African woman, not just as a family builder but also as a nation builder. The playwright through his plays has projected the African woman as a courageous, observant, strong willed, intelligent and a forceful being. He has also presented language as a tool that ignites consciousness and awareness as well as a vital instrument of revolt. He has creatively modified certain controversial aspects of the African society. The playwright through these plays has campaigned for change and insisted on women being given the opportunity to become politically active in their various societies.

The women in the two plays were extraordinarily courageous intelligent and strong willed in activism. These women exhibit great qualities of good leaders. They are forceful, daring, committed, and their dedicated examples restore peace, justice and progress to all in their respective communities. Through their sacrifices and efforts, their communities are able to look into the future with hope.

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